

**DISCOVERY OF NOVEL TRIAZOLE DERIVATIVES AS POTENTIAL
ANTIMICROBIAL AGENTS**

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ABSTRACT

This research has been successfully synthesized two compounds triazole derivatives by a twostep reaction. Firstly, triazole intermediate compounds were obtained by the reaction of appropriate hydrazide with suitable reagents in basic conditions. Then, triazole derivatives were obtained by cyclization of the intermediate compound in the presence of a dehydrating agent. Further substitution reactions were carried out to obtain different derivatives. The chemical structure of the synthesized compounds was confirmed by IR spectroscopy data analysis. Antibacterial activity of the compounds was evaluated by the agar well diffusion method. Biological evaluation results showed that triazole derivatives exhibited moderate antibacterial activity against *Bacillus subtilis* as compared to the benzotriazole derivatives.

KEYWORDS: Triazole, Antibacterial, *Bacillus subtilis*.

1. INTRODUCTION

Heterocyclic compound is the class of cyclic organic compounds those having at least one hetero atom (*i.e.* atom other than carbon) in the cyclic ring system. In the present unit, students would be able to learn about the common five and six membered heterocyclic compounds, such as Pyrrole, Furan, Thiophene, Pyridine and Piperidine etc.

Overview Of Triazole Derivatives

The name triazole was first coined by Bladin in 1885 to assign the five-membered three nitrogen-containing heterocyclic aromatic ring system having molecular formula $C_2H_3N_3$. Triazole heterocyclic structures are found to form many weak nonbond interactions with the receptors and enzymes in biological systems. Among the medicinal drugs, triazole-based antibacterial, antifungal, antiviral, anti-inflammatory, anticoagulant, antitubercular, antidiabetic, antioxidant, and anticancer drugs are available.

The appearance of multidrug-resistant (MDR) pathogens, especially, resistance to triazole drugs makes microbial

treatment less effective, a worse prognosis of infection, and problematic. Triazoles are molecules having a wide range of uses, including materials (polymers), agricultural chemicals, medicines, photoactive chemicals, and dyes. Because of its potential as chemotherapeutics, triazole and its derivatives have received a lot of interest in recent years.

Fig. 1: Mechanism of antibiotic action.

Physical Properties of triazole	
Chemical formula	$C_2H_3N_3$
Molar mass	69.07 g/mol
Appearance	White crystalline solid
Density	1.2 g/cm ³
Melting point	120 °C
Boiling point	250-260 °C
Solubility in water	Soluble

2 OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

1. To design novel triazole derivatives with potential biological activity.
2. To synthesize the designed triazole derivatives using suitable chemical methods.
3. To purify the synthesized compounds by appropriate techniques.
4. To determine the melting point of the synthesized compounds.

5. To characterize the synthesized compounds using analytical techniques such as IR.
6. To evaluate the pharmacological activity of the synthesized compounds (e.g., antimicrobial activity).
7. To compare the biological activity of synthesized compounds with standard drugs.
8. To identify the most active compound among the synthesized derivatives.
9. To conclude the potential of triazole derivatives as therapeutic agents.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

For Compound 1

Synthetic Scheme For Compound 1

Fig. 2: Synthetic scheme of compound 1

Procedure

Step 1

Benzotriazole is synthesized from o-phenylenediamine through a diazotization and cyclization reaction. First, o-phenylenediamine is dissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid, and the solution is cooled to a temperature of about 0–5°C using an ice bath. Maintaining this low temperature is essential for proper diazotization. Next, a cold aqueous solution of sodium nitrite is prepared separately and added slowly to the cooled reaction mixture with constant stirring. This step leads to the formation of a diazonium salt intermediate. The formed diazonium compound then undergoes an intramolecular cyclization reaction, resulting in the formation of the benzotriazole ring system. The reaction mixture is stirred for some time at low temperature and then allowed to gradually reach room temperature to complete the reaction. As the reaction proceeds benzotriazole begins to precipitate out of the solution. The solid product is then collected by filtration, washed with cold water to remove impurities, and finally purified by recrystallization using a suitable solvent such as ethanol. The final product obtained is benzotriazole, a heterocyclic compound containing three nitrogen atoms in its structure.

Step 2

N¹-Benzoyl benzotriazole is prepared by reacting benzotriazole with benzoyl chloride in the presence of sodium bicarbonate using distilled water as the reaction medium. Initially, benzotriazole is dissolved or suspended in distilled water, and an aqueous solution of sodium bicarbonate is added to maintain a mildly basic environment. The mixture is stirred thoroughly to ensure proper mixing of the reactants. Benzoyl chloride is then added slowly to the reaction mixture with continuous stirring. Sodium bicarbonate acts as a base and neutralizes the hydrochloric acid formed during the

reaction. The reaction proceeds through a nucleophilic substitution mechanism in which the nitrogen atom of benzotriazole attacks the carbonyl carbon of benzoyl chloride, resulting in the formation of N¹-benzoyl benzotriazole. During the reaction, effervescence occurs due to the evolution of carbon dioxide gas, indicating neutralization of the acid. The mixture is stirred for sufficient time to complete the reaction and then allowed to stand. The product precipitates out from the reaction mixture and is collected by filtration. The crude product is washed with distilled water to remove impurities and excess reagents. Finally, it is purified by recrystallization using a suitable solvent such as ethanol to obtain pure N¹-benzoyl benzotriazole.

Fig. 3: Structure of N¹ benzoyl benzotriazole.

Tlc Plate For Compound 1

Physical Data of Compound 1

IUPAC name	(1H-1,2,3-benzotriazole-1-yl)(phenyl) methanone
Molecular formula	C ₁₃ H ₉ N ₃ O
Molecular weight	223.23 g/mol
Melting point	96-100 °C
TLC	R _f value : 0.66
	Solvent system : chloroform: Ethanol: DMSO (6:3:1)
	Detecting Agent : Iodine chamber

IR Graph For Compound 1

Interpretation of compound 1 IR Data

Functional Group	Standard Peak (cm ⁻¹)	Observed Peak (cm ⁻¹)
2° Amine	1250-1000	1280
Ketone (carbonyl)	1900-1600	1653

For Compound 2

Synthetic Scheme For Compound 2

Fig. 04: Synthetic scheme of compound 2.

Procedure

Step 1

1,2,4-Triazole was synthesized by reacting formamide with hydrazine hydrate under reflux conditions. A measured quantity of formamide was taken in a round-bottom flask, and hydrazine hydrate was added slowly with continuous stirring. The reaction mixture was then heated under reflux at a temperature of about 160–180 °C for 4–6 hours to facilitate Condensation followed by cyclization. After completion of the reaction, the mixture was allowed to cool to room temperature and then poured into ice-cold water to induce precipitation of the product. The solid obtained was filtered, washed thoroughly with cold water to remove impurities, and dried. The crude product was further purified by recrystallization using ethanol to obtain pure 1,2,4-triazole.

Step 2

The synthesis of N¹-benzoyl-1,2,4-triazole was carried out by reflux method. A dry round bottom flask was taken and charged with 1,2,4-triazole and dry acetone as a reaction solvent and after add pyridine as a base. The mixture was stirred and a reflux condenser was attached to the flask. Benzoyl chloride was then added slowly dropwise with continuous stirring. The reaction mixture was heated under reflux on a water bath at 60–70°C for about 2–3 hours. During the reaction, hydrogen chloride gas was evolved, which was neutralized by pyridine. After completion of reflux, the reaction mixture was

allowed to cool to room temperature and then poured into ice-cold water with stirring. A white precipitate of crude product was formed immediately. The solid was collected by filtration and washed several times with cold water to remove impurities and pyridine salts. The crude product was then dried and purified by recrystallization from ethanol. The purified compound was obtained as white crystalline solid of N¹-benzoyl-1,2,4-triazole.

Tlc Plate For Compound 2

Physical Data of Compound 2

IUPAC name	Phenyl(1H-1,2,4-triazole-1-yl) methanone
Molecular formula	C ₉ H ₇ N ₃ O
Molecular weight	173.17 g/mol
Melting point	130-135 °C
TLC	Rf value : 0.84
	Solvent system : chloroform: Ethanol: DMSO (6:3:1)
	Detecting Agent : Iodine chamber

IR Graph For Compound 2

Interpretation of compound 1 IR Data

Functional Group	Standard Peak (cm ⁻¹)	Observed Peak (cm ⁻¹)
2° Amine-N	1250-1000	1287
Ketone C=O	1900-1600	1680

4. BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY OF NEWLY SYNTHESIZED COMPOUND

Microbial Screening

All above synthesized compounds were evaluated and tested for their antibacterial activity against *Bacillus subtilis* as Gram positive bacteria. Agar disc diffusion method was widely used for determination of the preliminary antibacterial. tetracycline used as a standard drug. The results were recorded for each tested compound as the average diameter of zone of inhibition of bacterial growth around the discs in mm.

Agar well Diffusion Method

composition of medium

- beef extract, peptone, agar, dist. water- 250ml, ph 7.0-7.2
- microorganism used
- bacillus subtilis
- standard drug used
- Tetracycline

Procedure

Step:1 Preparation of Agar medium Prepare MHA from the dehydrated medium according to the manufacturer's instructions. Media should be prepared using distilled water or deionized water.

Heat with frequent agitation and boil to dissolve the medium completely. Sterilize by autoclaving at 121°C for 15 min.

- Check the pH of each preparation after it is sterilized, which should be between 7.2 and 7.4 at room temperature.

- Cool the agar medium to 40-50°C. Pour the agar into sterile glass or plastic petri dish on a flat surface to a uniform depth of 4 mm.

- Allow to solidify.

- Prior to use, dry plates at 30-37°C in an incubator, with lids partly ajar, for not more than 30 minutes or until excess surface moisture has evaporated. Media must be moist but free of water droplets on the surface. Presence of water droplets may result to swarming bacterial growth, which could give inaccurate results. They are also easily contaminated.

Step: 2 Inoculum

- From a pure bacterial culture (not more than 48 hours, old except for slow growing organisms), take four or five colonies with a wire loop.

- Inoculate the agar by streaking with the swab containing the inoculum.

- Rotate the plate by 60° and repeat the rubbing procedure. Repeat two times. This will ensure an even distribution of the inoculum.

- Allow the surface of the medium to dry for 3-5 minutes but not longer than 15 minutes to allow for absorption of excess moisture.

Step: 3 Agar well diffusion

- The inoculated agar was poured into the assay plate (9 cm in diameter), and allowed to cool down on a leveled surface.
- Once the medium had solidified, four wells, each 4 mm in diameter, were cut out of the agar, and 20 μ l of the anti-fungal agent were placed into each well. A total of four antibacterial were placed into each plate and incubated at 35 °C for 24 hours.

• Because of disagreement over the criteria to determine the end point of the diameters of the clear zone of inhibition of growth, it was measured both at 50% and 80%.

Step: 4 Incubation

- Incubate plates in an inverted position at 30°C or at an optimum growth temperature.
- Observe for the zone of inhibition after 16 to 18 hours. Slow growing organisms may require longer incubation period.

Step: 5 Reading and Measurement of Zone of Inhibition

- The zone of inhibition is the point at which no growth is visible to the unaided eye.
- Record the presence of individual colonies within zones of inhibition.
- Read and record the diameter of the zones of inhibition using a ruler graduated to 0.5mm

Fig. 05: Biological Activity

Observation of Biological Activity

Synthesized Compound	Zone of Inhibition (mm)
Compound 1	17
Compound 2	20
Tetracycline (Standard)	25

Graph.

5. CONCLUSION

In this study, triazole derivative compounds were successfully synthesized by condensation of appropriate starting materials under suitable reaction conditions. The chemical structures of all the synthesized compounds were confirmed by IR spectroscopy analysis and further verified by TLC and melting point determination. The antimicrobial assay of triazole derivatives demonstrated significant antibacterial activity. Among the synthesized compounds, compound no. 2 exhibited higher antibacterial activity compared to compound no.1. This indicates that structural modification in the triazole ring system enhances antibacterial activity, suggesting that heterocyclic substitution plays an important role in

improving biological activity. Therefore, triazole derivatives show better antibacterial potential compared to benzotriazole derivatives.

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